

USE OF DRIP IRRIGATION METHOD WITH MINERALIZED WATERS IN GROWING COTTON CROP

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Abstract In the article, when drip irrigation with mineralized water is used in an experimental field where cotton is planted in moderately saline alluvial soils of the Bukhara region, with a seepage water level of 1.5–2.0 m, when the soil moisture before irrigation is 70-80-65% compared to ChDNS, cotton 3- It was watered 15 times according to the 10-2 scheme. Cotton was not irrigated during the period from germination to flowering, cotton was irrigated fifteen times with irrigation norms of 273-437 m³/ha during the period of flowering and fruiting, seasonal irrigation norm - 4483 m³/ha. or 1594 m³/ha of irrigation water was saved compared to the control option.

Key words: Cotton, water shortage, drip irrigation, irrigation rate, seasonal irrigation rate, seepage waters, mineralization, vegetation period.

The development of world agriculture is directly related to the level of water resources supply. is causing the need to introduce technologies. Because "by 2040, the population of the earth will reach nine billion, and fresh water resources will cover only 70% of human needs" will make the issue even more complicated [1].

In order to eliminate these problems, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6024 of July 10, 2020, "Concept of Water Management Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030", PQ-144 of March 1, 2022, "Introduction of Water-Saving Technologies in Agriculture" In

the decision "On measures to further improve water supply" and PQ-5005 dated February 24, 2021 "On approval of the strategy for the management of water resources and development of the irrigation sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2023", rational and economical use of water resources, reclamation of irrigated lands This research work serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks set to further improve the situation [3].

The purpose of the study. Scientifically based irrigation method of drip irrigation of cotton with mineralized water in the conditions of alluvial grassland of Bukhara region, heavy sand soils according to mechanical composition, seepage water level 1.5–2.0 m, mineralization 1.0–3.0 g/l and their development of scientific and practical recommendations for the study of cotton growth, development, yield, quality indicators of cotton fiber.

Figure 1. A view of the experimental field with drip irrigation

The tasks of the research are as follows:

- determination of soil conditions (type, mechanical composition, water-physical properties and fertility) of experimental fields;
- determination of hydrogeological and reclamation conditions of experimental fields;
- determination of scientifically based methods of irrigation by drip irrigation of cotton in the conditions of meadow alluvial soils of the Bukhara region, where the water level is 1.5–2.0 m and the mineralization is 1–3 g/l;
- the effect of the scientifically based irrigation method of cotton drip irrigation on the water-physical properties of the soil, salt regime, changes in the level and mineralization of seepage waters, their growth and development,

Field experiments Scientifically based irrigation of cotton by drip irrigation with mineralized water in the conditions of meadow alluvial, medium sandy loam soils according to mechanical composition with water table level of 1.5–2.0 m, mineralization of 1.0–3.0 g/l, Vobkent district, Bukhara region effects on its growth, development and productivity were studied [4,6]. Experiments were performed in the following systems (Table 1).

According to the description of N.A. Kachinsky, the mechanical composition of the soil of the experimental field belongs to the type of soils with a mechanical composition of heavy sand.

Table 1

№	Pre-sowing soil moisture, % relative to ChDNS	Irrigation method
1	production control	irrigation over land
2	70-80-65 %	Drip irrigation

The bulk density of the soil in the experimental field at the beginning of the growing season was 1.33–1.35 g/cm³ in the 0–30 cm layer of the plowed layer, 1.41–1.43 g/cm³ in the 30–50 cm layer below the plowed layer, and 0– It was 1.39–1.40 g/cm³ in a layer of 100 cm [5,7].

According to the data in Table 2, cotton was irrigated five times according to the irrigation 1-3-1 scheme during the growing season in the 1st control version of the experiment.

Table 2

Drip irrigation method of cotton

№	Options	Watering scheme	Seasonal irrigation norm, m ³ /ha
1	B-1	1-3-1	6077
2	B-2	3-10-2	4483

The following conclusions were reached based on the study of the scientifically based irrigation procedure in the drip irrigation technology of cotton in alluvial soils of the Bukhara oasis, which has been irrigated since ancient times: In the experimental field planted with cotton, the bulk density of the soil at the beginning of the growing season was 1.33–1.35 g/cm³ in the 0–30 cm layer under the plowed layer, 1.41–1.43 g/cm³ in the 30–50 cm layer below the cultivated layer, and 0–100 cm layer was 1.39–1.40 g/cm³. By the end of vegetation, in option 2, which was drip-irrigated, the volumetric weight of the soil was 1.34–1.35 g/cm³ in the 0–30 cm layer of the arable layer, 1.42–1.43 g/cm³ in the 30–50 cm layer below the arable layer, and It was 1.40–1.41 g/cm³ in the 0–100 cm layer. It was determined that the volume weight of the soil increased by 0.01 g/cm³, and this indicator was the lowest compared to other options.

Literature

- [1] Isaev S, Mardiev SH. Influence ameliorative condition of irrigated lands of the khorezm region on cotton fertility INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH CULTURE SOCIETY, Monthly, Peer-Reviewed, Refereed, Indexed Journal 2019/6/25 Accepted on:
- [2] Khamidov M K, Balla D, Hamidov A M., Juraev U A. Using collector-drainage water in saline and arid irrigation areas for adaptation to climate change. 2020. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 422(1),012121
- [3] Хамидов М Х, Жўраев У А. Influence of phytoremediation plants on soil salts // Innovative technologies in water management complex. – Ukraine, Rovno, 2012. – С. 32–34.
- [4] Isaev S, & Haidarov B. (2018). Drainage water use for cotton-plant irrigation. Bulletin of Science and Practice, 4(9), 109-113
- [5] Жураев А К, & Саксонов У С. (2019). Bug‘doy o‘simligining biologiyasi hamda agrotexnikasi. журнал агро процессинг, (6).

- [6] Murodov Otabek Ulugbekovich, Kattayev Bobir Sobirovich, Saylixanova Maftuna Komiljonovna, & Ibodov Islom Nizomiy o'g'li. (2020). Smart irrigation of agricultural crops. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 3, 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.47494/mesb.2020.3.16>
- [7] Жураев А К, & Саксонов У С. (2019). Вухоро vohasida kuzgi bug'doyni sug'orish muddatlari va me'yorlarini ilmiy asoslash. журнал агро процессинг, (6).
- [8] Murodov O U, Kattaev B S, Saylixanova M K. // The use of sprinkler irrigation in the cultivation of agricultural crops // " Proceeding of The ICECRS.Conference of Management of Islamic Education Leadership In The Era of Revolution 4.0 "conference. - Indonesia 2020.
- [9]. Murodov Otabek Ulugbekovich, Saylixanova Maftuna Komiljonovna, Kattayev Bobir Sobirovich, Muzaffarov Muxriddin Murodovich. [Determination of efficiency of groundwater use in irrigation of millet planting](#), Euro-Asia Conferences, 2021/3/31, 131-134.
- [10] Ruziyeva, M. A., Najmiddinov, M. M., & Sobirov, K. S. (2022). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF METHODS FOR MEASURING BURNUP OF SPENT FUEL ASSEMBLIES BETI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(5), 385-389.
- [11] Хамидов М Х, Жураев У А. Снижения минерализации коллекторно-дренажных вод //Аграрная наука. 2016. № 6. С. 2-3.
- [12] O U Murodov, U O Teshayev, O I Amrulloev, S U Islomov. [Determining the efficiency of the use of underground water in irrigation of tarik](#). Экономика и социум, 2021, 187-191.
- [13] U A Jo'rayev, A Q Jo'rayev, B N Atamurodov-Application of Provided Irrigation Technologies in Irrigated Agriculture, International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 2021 164-166 st.
- [14] Ro'Ziyeva, M. A., & Najmiddinov, M. M. (2022). Sho'rlik darajasi turlicha bo'lgan suvning jamadon tipidagi ko'chma quyosh suv chuchiktgich

- qurilmasining unumdorligiga ko'rsatadigan ta'siri. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 218-221.
- [15] A Q Jurayev, U A Jurayev, B N Atamurodov, M M Najmiddinov, Cultivation of Corn as a Repeated Crop, *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630) 2021/11/29 49-51 st.
- [16] Isaev, S. X., Juraev, A. Q., Juraev, U. A., Murodov, O. U., Najmiddinov, M. M., & Ruziyeva, M. A. (2022). Investigating irrigation system by using drainage water in the cultivation of repeated millet crop. *Journal of Advanced Scientific Research (ISSN: 0976-9595)*, 2(2).